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PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THREE-LAYER CEMENT BONDED BOARD PRODUCED FROM *Polyalthia longifolia* (Sonn.) FLAKES AND KRAFT PAPER

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ABSTRACT

Physical and mechanical properties of three layer cement bonded board produced from flakes of *Polyalthia longifolia* and kraft paper were assessed. The boards were produced with three different material blends and mixing ratio, material blends include pure paper, pure flakes (one layer) and paper/flakes(3-layer). The 3-layer boards were produced by using flakes to form the core and paper slurry for the face and back. Water absorption (WA), thickness swelling (TS), linear expansion (LE), and mechanical test; modulus of elasticity (MOE) and modulus of rupture (MOR) tests were conducted. The board formation was based on a mixing ratio of 1:1, 2:1, 3:1 i.e. cement to material blending proportion. The mean value for WA, TS, LE ranged from 29.23±2.18 % - 55.92±2.50 %, 1.93±1.62% - 5.74±2.61 %, 0.27±0.16 % - 0.51±0.19 % for PAPER+FLAKES, 25.86±2.18% - 58.69±4.90 %, 1.74±1.32 % - 4.52±2.05 %, 0.35±0.41 % - 0.65±0.48 % for PURE FLAKES while 38.82±6.80 % - 61.06±3.67 %, 0.51±0.63 % - 3.53±1.80 %, 0.36±0.33% - 3.96±6.42% were recorded for PURE PAPER respectively. The mean values of MOE and MOR ranged from 249.46±0.71 N/mm² - 727.26±2.82 N/mm² and 0.09±0.18 N/mm² - 0.26±0.11 N/mm² respectively. The physical property test showed that the inclusion of paper slurry forming the face and back with flake as the core (3-layer) influences the surface quality of the boards produced while the mechanical tests showed that the addition of flakes improves the strength properties.

Keywords: Strength Properties; Water Absorption; Thickness Swelling; Cement bonded board; Linear Expansion.

INTRODUCTION

Cement bonded board which are more dimensionally stable and are good construction materials which are of great importance to mankind and possess unique qualities over other boards. In developing countries like Nigeria, large quantities of wood residues are generated on daily basis during wood processing without recourse for economic use.

Technology as at today has helped to make use of wood wastes in production of different panel products as high pressure has been on the major source of timber i.e the forest. Increase in population and loss of forest lands to agricultural purposes due to ineffectiveness in the forest policy of the nation has provided various alternatives through different experiments such as use of sawdust, wood flakes, maize stalk, cotton stalk, baggase, banana stalk to produce panel products which includes cement bonded boards, fibre cement board, plastic board etc. The *Polyalthia longifolia* tree belongs to the *Annonaceae* family, native to India and Sri lanka which could be a prime choice of landscape designers and gardeners. It is popularly called the mast tree with a narrow, broadly columnar shape, much taller than broad. The trunk is straight and slender, commonly propagated by seeds. (Liamas, K. 2003).

Due to loss of biodiversity of various tree species that provides wood and high cost of the other panel products, this has prompt the investigation of wood wastes such as flakes and kraft paper which are always burnt thereby causing air pollution, can be used to produce cement bonded board. This will not only reduce emanating from wood waste burning but will also contribute to economic growth of the country and reduce pressure on trees from the forest (Ajayi, 2004). Only about 50 – 55% of the original wood harvested becomes marketable after processing in sawmills scattered across the country shows that large volume of saw dust and wood flakes are burnt on daily basis, thus constituting a major environmental problem (Ajayi, 2004). The economic benefit of waste residues is to incorporate the wood residues (flakes) into the production of cement bonded board which can be used for roofing, ceiling board, flooring, partitioning, cladding and shuttering (Sotannde *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, it is necessary to look into the conversion of waste to wealth thereby increasing source of income and employment opportunities also minimizing the rate of wastes leading to different types of environmental pollution. The objective of this study is to investigate the physical and mechanical properties of a cement bonded board produced from *Polyalthia longifolia* flakes and kraft paper.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Polyalthia longifolia tree was fell from a free area in the Federal University of Technology Akure, Ondo State and converted into flakes after treated with boiled water. The kraft paper slurry milled from waste cartons added with Calcium chloride was prepared for the board formulation. The quantities of materials required to produce a board of 350 (width) × 350 (length) × 12 mm (thickness) were calculated and measured based on pre-determine blending proportion. 3% calcium chloride was used as an additive while water was added using the procedures of Simatupang (1979) expressed as:

$$\text{Water (in litre)} = 0.35C + (0.03-MC) W \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

Where: C = Weight of cement (kg), MC=Particle moisture content, (oven-dry basis) and W = weight of oven-dry particles (kg).

The quantity of flakes, paper and cement required to produce the boards were weighed differently using the weighing balance. The flakes were mixed manually with water containing calcium chloride before cement was gradually added and thoroughly hand- mixed until a homogeneous mixture was formed. The mixture was evenly distributed into a mould of 350 by 350 by 12 mm on the caul plates covered with a cellophane nylon (to prevent sticking of the board to the plate). Another caul plate was placed on the felted mattress which was pre-pressed to ensure uniformity of the mixture. The pre-pressed board was pressed to stop under hydraulic press (2.3N/mm²). After 24 hours of pressing, the board was removed from the caul plates and sealed in the polythene bags for 2 days and then stacked in the laboratory for 28 days curing. Boards were produced from pure flakes, pure paper and three layer with

the flakes as the core. Thereafter, the boards were trimmed using the circular saw and cut into test samples of 195 by 50 mm for mechanical test modulus of elasticity (MOE) and modulus of rupture (MOR) was calculated using equation 2 and 3 while ASTM 1037 (1998) standard was used to determine the physical test with 150 by 150 mm for Water Absorption, Thickness Swelling and Linear Expansion.

$$\text{MOE} = \frac{PL^3}{4BD^2} \quad \text{Eq.2}$$

Where: MOE = Modulus of elasticity (N/mm²)

P = Load (N)

L = life span of load of board samples between the machine supports (mm)

b = width of the board sample (mm)

d = thickness of the board sample (mm)

$$\text{MOR} = \frac{3PL}{2bd^2} \quad \text{Eq.3}$$

Where; MOR = Modulus of rupture (N/mm²)

P = the ultimate failure load (N)

L = the board span between supports (mm)

b = width of the board sample (mm)

d = thickness of the board sample (mm)

The statistical design for the experiment was 3 × 3 factorial experiment in Completely Randomized Design, the combination of which gave 9 treatments and total of 27 boards. Analysis of variance was carried out to determine the significant effect of the factors of production on boards properties and Duncan Multiple Ratio Test (DMRT) method was used to determine the significance of observed differences in sample means at 0.05 levels of significance.

RESULTS

Water Absorption

The mean values for Water absorption as shown in Table 1 ranged from 25.86±1.40% - 61.06±1.33% thus revealing that the boards produced with pure paper had the highest rate of water absorption while the boards produced with paper/flakes had the lowest rate of water absorption. Analysis of Variance in Table 2 shows that there is significant difference in the blending proportion, mixing ratio and also in the interaction between the blending proportion and the mixing ratio on the rate of water absorption of the boards produced after soaking for 24 hours. Table 4 shows that there is significant difference in the blending proportion and mixing ratio on the rate of water absorption of the boards produced and in the interaction between the blending proportion and the mixing ratio on the rate of water absorption of the boards produced using ($p \leq 0.05$), after soaking for 48 hours. Table 2 also indicate the significant effects of the blending proportion, mixing ratio and the interaction between both on the rate of water absorption of the boards after soaking for 72 hours. Table 3 shows The Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) on the blending proportion of the boards produced with pure flakes revealed that water absorption shows no significant difference between the hours of soaking (24hours, 48 hours and 72 hours respectively)

Table 1: Mean Value

BLENDING PROPORTION	MIXING RATIO	WA.24HR (%)	WA.48HR (%)	WA.72HR (%)	TS.24HR (%)	TS.48HR (%)	TS.72HR (%)	LE.24HR (%)	LE.48HR (%)	LE.72HR (%)
PAPER+FLAKES	1:1	50.24±1.99	51.77±1.75	55.92±2.50	5.74±2.61	4.28±6.80	4.04±4.69	0.46±0.36	0.41±0.28	0.51±0.19
	2:1	34.42±2.46	35.82±2.41	38.76±2.81	3.30±1.85	3.14±2.22	3.10±2.66	0.45±0.27	0.39±0.24	0.38±0.23
	3:1	29.23±5.56	29.57±5.74	31.95±5.78	4.75±7.02	1.93±1.62	2.55±1.15	0.31±0.22	0.29±0.17	0.27±0.16
PURE FLAKES	1:1	51.46±4.65	54.25±3.18	58.69±4.90	4.52±2.05	3.62±1.64	3.07±1.05	0.52±0.38	0.53±0.45	0.65±0.48
	2:1	36.51±5.47	37.57±4.04	41.51±3.00	2.82±2.09	3.15±1.69	2.27±1.25	0.46±0.73	0.43±0.46	0.56±0.94
	3:1	25.86±2.18	26.57±2.00	28.60±1.48	2.04±1.56	1.74±1.32	4.08±2.08	0.35±0.41	0.40±0.70	0.38±0.76
PURE PAPER	1:1	59.49±3.70	58.96±3.19	61.06±3.67	2.81±0.93	2.78±1.71	3.53±1.80	3.96±6.42	3.68±6.27	3.65±6.28
	2:1	55.00±1.23	55.61±7.13	56.86±6.83	0.86±1.00	1.64±1.46	1.91±2.86	0.58±0.58	0.36±0.33	0.72±0.49
	3:1	38.82±6.80	39.42±1.06	40.11±0.93	0.51±0.63	0.72±2.23	0.83±1.41	0.47±0.53	0.62±0.50	0.43±0.32

Table 2: Analysis of Variance for Water Absorption for 24, 48 and 72 hours

Source	24 (Fcal)	48 (Fcal)	72(Fcal)	df
B.P	3112.96 (88.29*)	2624.22 (87.50*)	1843.89 (57.73*)	2
M.R	5259.23 (149.17*)	5555.76 (185.26*)	6458.95 (202.21*)	2
B.P*M.R	2003.89 (28.42*)	2263.62 (37.74*)	2598.61 (40.68*)	4
ERROR	1269.22	1079.63	1149.91	72
TOTAL	11645.31	11523.22	12051.36	80

*significant (p< 0.05) ^{ns}not significant (p> 0.05)

MR*BP denotes interaction between mixing ratio and blending proportion

Table 3: Duncan Multiple Range Test for Blending Proportion and Mixing Ratio of WA, TS &LE

	WA	WA	WA	TS	TS	TS	LE	LE	LE
	24	48	72	24	48	72	24	48	72
PURE FLAKES	37.94 ^b	39.46 ^b	42.93 ^b	3.12 ^a	2.84 ^a	3.13 ^a	0.44 ^b	0.45 ^a	0.53 ^a
PAPER/FLAKES	37.97 ^b	39.06 ^b	42.21 ^b	4.60 ^a	3.11 ^a	3.23 ^a	0.41 ^b	0.36 ^a	0.39 ^a
PURE PAPER	51.10 ^a	51.33 ^a	56.67 ^a	1.39 ^b	1.71 ^a	2.09 ^a	1.67 ^a	1.55 ^a	1.60 ^a
1:1	53.73 ^a	54.99 ^a	58.55 ^a	4.35 ^a	2.77 ^a	3.05 ^a	1.64 ^a	1.54 ^a	1.60 ^a
2:1	36.58 ^b	37.60 ^b	40.13 ^b	1.95 ^b	2.17 ^a	2.43 ^a	0.38 ^b	0.36 ^a	0.46 ^a
3:1	36.70 ^b	37.25 ^b	39.14 ^b	2.81 ^b	2.71 ^a	2.98 ^a	0.50 ^{ab}	0.47 ^a	0.46 ^a

Alphabets with the same letter show that there is no significant difference

Alphabets with different letter show that there is significant difference

Thickness Swelling

The mean values for thickness swelling as shown in Table 1 ranged from 0.51±0.95 % - 5.74±0.95% showing that boards produced with pure paper had the lowest rate of thickness swelling while the boards produced with paper/flakes had the highest rate of thickness swelling. ANOVA (Table 4) shows that there is a significant effect of the blending proportion and mixing ratio on the swelling but indicate no significant difference in the interaction between the blending proportion and the mixing ratio of the boards produced after soaking for 24 hours, while there is no significant effect of the blending proportion and mixing ratio on the rate of thickness swelling and also in the interaction between the blending proportion and mixing ratio on the rate of thickness swelling of the boards produced after soaking for 48 hours. Table 2 indicates no significant effect of the blending proportion and mixing ratio on the rate of thickness swelling and it shows no significant difference between the interaction of the blending proportion and the mixing ratio on the rate of thickness swelling after soaking for 72hours. Table 3 showed the Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) on the blending proportion of the boards produced shows that there is a significant difference in the thickness swelling between the hours of 24 hours and 48 hours while there is no significant different between in thickness swelling between 48 hours and 72 hours.

Table 4: Analysis of Variance for Thickness swelling 24, 48 and 72 hours

Source	24 (F cal)	48 (F cal)	72 (F cal)	df
B.P	138.99 (8.60*)	29.72 (1.88 ^{ns})	21.61(1.93 ^{ns})	2
M.R	80.25 (4.97*)	5.97 (0.38 ^{ns})	6.26 (0.56 ^{ns})	2
B.P*M.R	3.40 (0.11 ^{ns})	55.14 (1.74 ^{ns})	51.70 (2.31 ⁿ) ^s	4
ERROR	581.78	569.20	403.14	72
TOTAL	804.42	660.03	482.72	80

*significant (p< 0.05)

^{ns}not significant (p> 0.05)

MR*BP denotes interaction between mixing ratio and blending proportion

Linear Expansion

Table 1 showed the mean values for linear expansion ranged from $0.27 \pm 0.72\%$ - $3.96 \pm 0.73\%$ indicating that the boards produced with paper/flakes had the lowest rate of linear expansion and the highest rate of linear expansion falls within boards produced with pure paper. Table 5 shows that there is no significant effect of the blending proportion and mixing ratio on the rate of linear expansion and also there is no significant difference in the interaction between the blending proportion and mixing ratio on the rate of thickness swelling at 24 hours. Table 5 shows no significant difference on the blending ratio and mixing ratio on the rate of linear expansion at 48 hours, also indicates no significant difference in the interaction between the blending proportion and the mixing ratio of the boards produced after soaking for 48 hours. Table 5 shows no significant effect of the blending proportion and the mixing ratio on the rate of linear expansion, also no significant difference in the interaction between the blending proportion and the mixing ratio. The Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) showed in Table 3 on the blending proportion of the boards produced also shows that there is no significant difference in the linear expansion between the hours of soaking (24 hours, 48 hours and 72 hours respectively).

Table 5: Analysis of Variance for Linear Expansion 24, 48 and 72 hours

Source	24 (F cal)	48 (F cal)	72 (F cal)	df
B.P	27.81 (2.92 ^{ns})	23.75 (2.62 ^{ns})	23.63 (2.56 ^{ns})	2
M.R	26.43 (2.77 ^{ns})	22.96 (2.54 ^{ns})	23.68 (2.56 ^{ns})	2
B.P*M.R	44.55 (2.34 ^{ns})	38.66 (2.14 ^{ns})	34.18 (1.85 ^{ns})	4
ERROR	343.39	325.95	332.77	72
TOTAL	442.18	411.32	414.26	80

*significant ($p < 0.05$) ^{ns}not significant ($p > 0.05$)

MR*BP denotes interaction between mixing ratio and blending proportion

Modulus of Elasticity

Table 6 revealed the mean values for MOE ranged from $249.46 \pm 0.63 \text{ N/mm}^2$ - $727.26 \pm 0.63 \text{ N/mm}^2$. Table 7 indicated that there is no significant effect of the blending proportion and the mixing ratio on the MOE but there is a significant difference between the interaction of the blending proportion and the mixing ratio on the rate of MOE. The Duncan Multiple Range Test in Table 8 revealed that alphabets with same letter showed that there was no significant difference, alphabets with different letter showed that there was a significant difference. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the blending proportion of pure flakes and paper/flakes while there is a significant difference between (pure flakes, paper/flakes) and pure paper. Also there is a significant difference between the blending proportions (pure flakes, paper/flakes & pure paper) of the MOE having different alphabets a,b,c, while Table shows the significant difference between the mixing ratio of physical properties.

Table 6: Mean Value for Modulus of Elasticity and Modulus of Rupture

BLENDING PROPORTION	MIXING RATIO	MOE (N/mm ²)	MOR (N/mm ²)
PAPER+FLAKES	1:1	452.25±0.87	0.20±0.48
PAPER+FLAKES	2:1	500.06±0.78	0.19±0.23
PAPER+FLAKES	3:1	553.35±2.60	0.18±0.34
PURE FLAKES	1:1	520.03±2.60	0.26±0.11
PURE FLAKES	2:1	639.93±2.71	0.20±0.57
PURE FLAKES	3:1	727.26±2.82	0.15±0.45
PURE PAPER	1:1	249.46±0.71	0.12±0.45
PURE PAPER	2:1	345.55±0.82	0.11±0.22
PURE PAPER	3:1	431.11±0.91	0.09±0.18

Table 7: Analysis of Variance for MOE and MOR

Source	MOE (F cal)	MOR (F cal)	Df
B.P	111.57 (15.62*)	0.14 (28.81*)	2
M.R	17.53 (2.45 ^{ns})	0.03 (6.74*)	2
B.P*M.R	21.45 (1.50 ^{ns})	0.02 (2.42 ^{ns})	4
ERROR	257.17	0.18	72
TOTAL	407.71	0.38	80

*significant (p< 0.05) ^{ns}not significant (p> 0.05)

MR*BP denotes interaction between mixing ratio and blending proportion

Table 8: Duncan Multiple Range Test for Blending proportion and Mixing ratio on MOE & MOR

	MOR (N/mm ²)	MOE (N/mm ²)
PURE FLAKES	0.20 ^a	6.28 ^a
PAPER/FLAKES	0.19 ^a	5.02 ^b
PURE PAPER	0.11 ^b	3.42 ^c
1:1	0.19 ^a	479.39 ^{ab}
2:1	0.17 ^a	553.35 ^a
3:1	0.14 ^b	441.11 ^b

Modulus of Rupture

The mean values for MOR ranged from, 0.09±0.02 N/mm² - 0.26±0.11 N/mm². Table 7 shows that there is a significant effect of the blending proportion and the mixing ratio on the MOR but there is no significant difference in the interaction between the blending proportion and mixing ratio on the MOR. The Duncan Multiple Range Test revealed that alphabets with same letter showed that there was no significant difference, alphabets with different letter showed that there was a significant difference. Table 8 showed the significant difference between the mixing ratio on physical properties.

DISCUSSION

Effect of Mixing Ratio and Blending Proportion on Physical Properties of Cement Bonded Board

The dimensional stability of cement bonded boards varied based on the rate at which it can withstand the physical tests. The physical properties explain the rate at which the boards can absorb water, rate of thickness swelling and also its rate at which it can expand on linear section. The effect of these properties influenced the outcome of the cement bonded boards produced as reported by Aggarwal *et.al.*, (2008). The Physical Properties examined in this study are water absorption, thickness swelling and linear expansion i.e. the three layer board, therefore possess more dimensional stability property of the board. The mixing ratio of cement to particle type 3:1,2:1, 1:1 shows that the 3:1 that has more cement ratio is more dimensionally stable in response to the physical tests evaluation, which is similar to Simatupang (1991) reported that board properties such as water absorption, thickness swelling and linear expansion can be modified positively by proper addition of the mixing ratio of cement to particle which showed higher values of water absorption in boards with pure paper and lowest value in boards made with paper/flakes type. Ogunrinde O.S. (2012) also reported that boards produced from the highest mixing aggregate and blending proportion are more and highly dimensionally stable than others, whereby this study results shows relatively the same result as the 3:1 board is more dimensionally stable while the boards with paper/flakes having the highest blending proportion remains more stable than boards produced from pure paper and pure flakes.

Water Absorption

This study shows that rate of water absorption at 24 hours, 48 hours, and 72 hours was recorded to have the highest value in boards produced with pure paper while the lowest occurs in boards produced in 3-layer and simultaneously, boards produced with mixing ratio of 3:1 had the highest rate of water absorption while the lowest occurs in boards produced with mixing ratio of 1:1 therefore making the 3-layer boards possess a higher dimensional stability property and boards with mixing ratio of 1:1 have a high physical property than the other mixing ratios in terms of water absorption.

Thickness Swelling

This study shows that rate of thickness swelling at 24hours, 48hours, and 72hours that boards produced with pure paper the lowest rate of thickness swelling while boards produced in 3-layer had an average rate of thickness swelling and pure flakes had the highest rate of thickness swelling. Simultaneously, boards produced with mixing ratio of 3:1 had the highest rate of thickness swelling while the lowest occurs in boards produced with mixing ratio of 1:1 therefore making the 3-layer boards possess a higher dimensional stability property and boards with mixing ratio of 3:1 have a high physical property than the other mixing ratios in terms of thickness swelling

Linear Expansion

This study shows that rate of linear expansion at 24 hours, 48 hours, and 72 hours was recorded to have the highest value in boards produced with pure paper while the lowest occurs in boards produced in 3-layer and simultaneously, boards produced with mixing ratio of 3:1 had the highest rate of water absorption while the lowest occurs in boards produced with mixing ratio of 1:1 therefore making the 3-layer boards possess a higher dimensional stability property and boards with mixing ratio of 1:1 have a high physical property than the other mixing ratios in terms of linear expansion.

Effect of Blending Proportion and Mixing Ratio On Mechanical Properties of Cement Bonded Boards

Modulus of Elasticity (MOE)

This study shows that the results of the modulus of elasticity (MOE) reveals that the boards produced with pure flakes had the highest MOE value followed by the boards made from paper/flakes while the boards made from pure paper had the lowest MOE, MOE value. This result is in line with the study earlier reported by Badejo, (1989) that particles with a high slenderness ratio i.e longer and thinner particles, forms stronger and more dimensionally stable boards, which reflects in this study as flakes had longer particles thereby making boards that are formed from pure flakes more dimensionally stable than others. Therefore, the boards produced with pure flakes is a better choice in terms of mechanical property while the boards produced with pure paper is weak in terms of mechanical property. Also, the effect of mixing ratio on the modulus of elasticity shows that there is a higher value in boards produced with high cement to particle ratio as in 3:1, 2:1 unlike the low value in 1:1 therefore reveals that the higher ratio of cement to particles gives more stiffness and strength property

Modulus of Rupture (MOR)

The test samples were subjected to flexural tests (Modulus of Rupture) in accordance with American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM D570-98 2005). The bending strength test was assessed using test specimen of 195 × 50 × 12mm subjected to 3-point loading on Hunsfield Tensiometer machine. Each of the test specimens was supported by two rollers and loaded at the center. The forward movement of the machine leads to gradual increase of load at the middle span until failure of the test specimen occurs. At the point of failure, the force exerted on the specimen was recorded. The boards have no grain arrangement therefore the particle orientation forms the board and its ability to withstand all this improves its end-use. The effect of mixing ratio on the mechanical properties also shows that there is a higher value in boards produced with high cement to particle ratio as in 3:1, 2:1 unlike the low value in 1:1 therefore reveals that the higher ratio of cement to particles gives more stiffness and strength property as earlier reported by Ma *et. al.*, (2002) who compared his results of MOE & MOR of the boards produced showing that low amount of cement reduces the stiffness of the boards having known well that cement is stiffer than wood. This therefore shows the flexural, stiffness and strength property tests carried out on boards produced reveals satisfactory values comparing with earlier reports.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study had proved the suitability of the flakes and kraft paper for the production of cement bonded ceiling board and the compatibility of the paper and flakes improved the physical properties and mechanical properties of the boards produced with pure paper. The three-layered cement bonded board has the least rate of water absorption, thickness swelling and linear expansion thereby making boards produced with paper/flakes a better choice in terms of physical properties. Also boards produced from mixing ratio of 3:1 shows more strength property due to the increased quantity of cement while boards produced from mixing ratio of 1:1 had low water absorption, thickness swelling and linear expansion rate while boards produced from mixing ratio of 3:1 absorbs more water, and swells at a high rate thereby making the boards produced with mixing ratio of 1:1 a better choice in terms of physical properties. The thickness swelling properties of the boards were more affected by cement mixing ratio than the blending proportion. However, the three-layered cement bonded board could be suitable for ceiling application due to its low water absorption rate which will be of advantage when leakage occurs in roofing and could be used for outdoor wall cladding treatments.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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